

EFFECTIVE NITROGEN AND MOISTURE MANAGEMENT TECHNIQUES IN TOMATO PRODUCTION IN KADAWA, NIGERIA

Ainika, J. N¹ and Salako, O²

¹*Department of Agronomy, Institute for Agricultural Research,
Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria.*

²*Agricultural Research Council of Nigeria, Plot 223d Cadastral Zone B6,
Mabushi District, Abuja.*

Corresponding author: ndajoseph30@gmail.com GSM 08058201102

ABSTRACT

Two field trials were conducted in the dry season of 2017 and 2018 at the Irrigation Research Farm of the Institute for Agricultural Research, Kadawa, Kano state (11°39' N 080° 027' E, 500 m above sea level) in the Sudan savanna ecological zone of Nigeria to determine effective nitrogen and moisture management techniques in tomato production in Kadawa, Nigeria. Treatments consisted of four nitrogen regimes (Mineral fertilizer, Poultry droppings and Mineral fertilizer + Poultry droppings at recommended rate of 90 kg N ha⁻¹ with a control (No application) and two organic mulching materials (Rice straw and Sugar-cane peels) at recommended rates of 5.5 t ha⁻¹ and 11.0 t ha⁻¹ (4 cm thick), respectively, with a control (No mulch). The treatments were factorially combined and arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) and replicated three times. Tomato yield attribute as well as marketable fruit yield were significantly enhanced by nitrogen sourced from organic sources (poultry manure and mineral fertilizer + poultry manure than the unfertilized plots (control) while inorganic nitrogen sources contributed the lowest effect. Based on the results obtained from this study it can be concluded that poultry droppings at recommended rate of 2.88 t⁻¹ should be applied for higher productivity (marketable yield) of tomato on sustainable bases while the performance of the two mulching materials in soil moisture management is comparable but cost and return analysis has shown that sugar-cane peels mulch is recommended as suitable replacement to rice straw mulch for increased yield of tomato in the Sudan savanna ecological zone of Nigeria.

Keywords: Tomato, Nitrogen, moisture, Savanna, Kadawa
